

3 I300V, 1 V300I

I
V

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

3 I300V, 1 V300I

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

3 I300V, 1 V300I

I
V

shallow
intermediate
deep
NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

3 I300V, 1 V300I

I
V

shallow
intermediate
deep
NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12